

QUIZ**LAST NAME: PANTUVO****FIRST NAME: JERRY****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. The order of elements in notes-bibliography entries follows which of the following general pattern for all types of sources?**
 - Author, date, facts of publication.
 - Author, title, facts of publication.¹**
 - Author, date (year) of publication, title of publication.
 - Author, facts of publication, title.

- 2. A comprehensive review of literature in a dissertation should accomplish several distinct objectives except?**
 - Frame the research problem by setting it within a larger context.
 - Focus the purpose of the study more precisely.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 92.

- Contribute to analysis and interpretation of study's findings.
 - Link research findings to future studies.²**
3. **Which of the following is NOT an area of information needed in qualitative research?**
- Contextual information.
 - Demographic information.
 - Perceptual information.
 - Quantifiable information.³**
4. **Each paragraph in the body of an essay should contain?**
- Introduction, methodology, data analysis, discussion, and conclusion.
 - Conceptual framework, analysis, body, structure.
 - Topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence, analysis, and critical conclusion.⁴**
 - Creative thinking, critical thinking, referencing, citation style.
5. **Having a house style for citation in an organization offers the following advantages except**
- Consistency.
 - Contributes to the corporate image of the organization.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 62.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 69.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

- Increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process.
- None of the above.**⁵

6. **One does not need to cite when?**

- The information you are writing about is common knowledge.**⁶
- The source is unpublished.
- The author is unknown (Anonymous).
- Information is from electronic media.

7. **The goal of a research project includes the following (Tick all that apply)**

- Ask a question worth answering.**⁷
- Convince the readers that you are right about your claims.
- Find an answer that you can support with good reasons.**
- Find reliable evidence to support your reasons.**

8. **A writer can be accused of plagiarism if he does any or all of the following.**

- Cites a source but uses its exact source without putting them in quotation marks.
- Paraphrases and cites a source but its words are so similar to those of the source.
- Uses ideas or methods from a source but fails to cite it.

⁵ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (WHO, 2004), 1.

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 9.

⁷ Turabian, 18.

- All of the above.**⁸
9. **The elements in a citation format should aim to answer the following except**
- Who wrote, edited, or translated the text?
 - What data identify the text?
 - Who published the text and when?
 - How many people have used the text?**⁹
10. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, if a publication has several authors, how are they correctly referenced regarding their first and last names?**
- The names of all authors are inverted.
 - None of the author's names are inverted.
 - When there are more than six authors, one should only reference the first author and then use "et al."
 - Only the first listed author's name is in inverted order; names of additional authors follow but are inverted.**¹⁰

⁸ Turabian, 51.

⁹ Turabian, 87.

¹⁰ Turabian, 138.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation : A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

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